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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Motivación estudiantil en humanidades: Su impacto en el rendimiento académico y desarrollo profesional
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Resumen

En el proceso de la enseñanza superior, se reestructura el sistema de relaciones vitales de los estudiantes con la realidad y se transforman los motivos principales de su actividad, lo que afecta a los resultados de sus estudios. En este contexto, la exploración del rendimiento académico de los estudiantes adquiere mayor importancia en vista del aumento de los requisitos que se exigen a los titulados universitarios de hoy en día. La especificidad de la educación humanitaria orienta a los estudiantes hacia la necesidad de actualizar constantemente sus conocimientos y obtener formación adicional en disciplinas afines y, por lo tanto, depende de la motivación de los estudiantes para aprender. El objetivo del estudio es determinar el efecto de los tipos de motivación en los estudiantes de humanidades sobre su rendimiento académico y el nivel de formación profesional utilizando el enfoque del estudio de casos y el análisis de correlaciones. Los resultados obtenidos demuestran que la motivación de logro se relaciona con el éxito en el aprendizaje y la concentración de los estudiantes en el proceso educativo. Se observan correlaciones entre 1) el rendimiento académico y la motivación de logro; 2) el rendimiento académico y los indicadores cuantitativos de motivación de éxito, revelando el análisis cualitativo una correlación entre un mayor rendimiento académico y una mayor motivación de éxito en la mayoría de los estudiantes; 3) el tipo de motivación para la formación universitaria y el rendimiento académico.

Palabras clave: motivación de logro, motivación de aprendizaje, profesión, educación.

Abstract

Student Motivation in Humanities: Its Impact on Academic Performance and Professional Development

In the process of higher education, the system of students' life relations with reality is restructured and the leading motives of activity are transformed, which affects the results of their studies. In this context, exploring students' academic performance becomes more important in view of the increased requirements for today's university graduates. The specificity of humanitarian education directs students towards the need to constantly update their knowledge and obtain additional education in related

disciplines and, therefore, depends on students' motivation for learning. The purpose of the study is to determine the effect of motivation types in humanities students on their academic performance and the level of professional training using the case study approach and correlation analysis. The obtained results demonstrate that motivation for achievement relates to success in learning and students' focus on the educational process. Correlations are observed between 1) academic performance and achievement motivation; 2) academic performance and the quantitative indicators of motivation for success, with qualitative analysis revealing a correlation between higher academic performance and higher success motivation in most students; 3) the type of motivation for university education and academic performance.

Key words: achievement motivation, learning motivation, profession, education.

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1.- Introduction

Today's labor market demands highly qualified and competitive specialists (Winter et al., 2021). An important aspect of an employer's work is searching for and attracting young specialists who strive to achieve the set goals, can solve professional tasks quickly and with high quality (Shebzukhova et al., 2023), and are motivated to obtain new knowledge (Yulina et al., 2022). A professional orientation focused on achieving success is possible in any field, but only if the worker has a sufficient level of motivation for achievement with an overall focus on success (Wagner et al., 2023).

Of particular interest is academic motivation, since motives have a direct impact on the quality of professional training (Naydenova, 2021) and the development of the professional's personality (Shafazhinskaya et al., 2023). Modern students often struggle with learning motivation (Panikarova et al., 2021). Specifically, they lack the desire to learn and make the effort to study any discipline seriously (Maloshonok et al., 2015). For this reason, there is an increasing urgency to study the impact of motivation as a factor in successful professional performance. Young specialists need to be aware that in the humanities, it is necessary to be constantly engaged in the process of acquiring

new knowledge, additional professional education, and competencies and skills that provide competitiveness and professional mobility in the labor market.

Literature review

The overwhelming majority of researchers (Semenova, 2015; Sokolovskaya et al., 2020; Savenkov & Gavrilova, 2021) believe that regardless of whether achievement motivation is intrinsic or extrinsic, its essence is defined by the individual's need to achieve success in a particular activity.

The concept of the structure of motivation is interpreted in psychology as a hierarchy of motives, the dominance of some motives over others, and the overriding importance of certain specific motives for achieving the final goal.

Given that success is associated with the intellectual, motivational, emotional, and volitional spheres of the personality, success in learning is defined by the degree of correspondence between the real and intended results of learning and includes an objective (the obtained results) and subjective (self-assessment of academic performance) component (Ivaniushina et al., 2016). The psychological criteria of academic success include a positive learning motivation, a positive attitude toward the educational institution, and retention of cognitive interest; social adaptability; positive relations in the academic group; good physical and mental health (Kashina et al., 2023); and adequate positive self-esteem (Aleksandrova et al., 2023). Thus, academic performance represents the totality of performance in learning activities, the effectiveness of ways to achieve goals, and subjective satisfaction with the process and results of learning.

The decisive factor in academic success is motivation for achievement as a type of motivation that is closely tied to the need for achievement and striving for success in various spheres (Danilova, 2016). As a factor in successful learning, motivation for achievement is mediated by learning motivation (Borodina et al., 2023).

Intrinsic motivation for learning includes deep motives behind enrolling in a university and broad educational-cognitive and self-education motives, which foster greater interest in learning, academic success, intellectual satisfaction, and self-realization. Extrinsic motivation, in contrast, refers to superficial motives for enrolling in a university and narrow cognitive motives dependent on external support (to keep up with coursemates, gain teachers' respect, and avoid judgment and punishment) (Gorlova et al., 2023).

Among the types of motivation, researchers distinguish positive and negative motivation for learning (Borodina et al., 2022; Shevchuk et al., 2023). Positive motivation is directly connected to the educational process and the chosen profession and includes cognitive and professional motives. Students guided by positive motivation experience the need to gain new knowledge, are inquisitive and eager to learn new things, and enjoy raising their level of knowledge when mastering the studied material (Sokolnikov, 2018). Negative motivation is understood as the student's striving to learn

driven by the recognition of certain inconveniences and troubles that may arise if they do not study. The latter type includes pragmatic motives (obtaining a diploma) that imply studying without striving to learn the material, interest in the profession, or desire to attend the educational institution (Semenova, 2016).

Several researchers have established that a high positive motivation can act as a compensatory factor in the case of a student lacking in abilities. However, no high level of ability can compensate for the lack of positive learning motivation or its low level and bring significant success in learning (Dvoretzkaia & Akhmadieva, 2018). Therefore, learning motivation can be considered another factor affecting the student's academic performance, especially in profile disciplines. The specificity of contemporary higher education is that it is an environment that relies on information and communications technology (Pivneva et al., 2023) and educational resources and services of information and communications networks that provide support for learning, activity, and personality development (Bogatyreva et al., 2022). Under such conditions, it is vital for the student to develop their personal qualities, such as striving for self-organization (Eflova et al., 2023), discipline, and quick adaptation to change (Merezhko et al., 2023). With positive learning motivation, it is much easier for the student to develop personality qualities that will ultimately improve their academic performance and the level of professional training (Moreva & Skitnevskaya, 2023). Furthermore, academic performance is affected by specific learning conditions (Gadzaova et al., 2023), the university's methodical material and technical equipment, the cultural and national specifics under which the educational process proceeds, as well as financial welfare. However, as evidenced by numerous studies, intrinsic motivation is the leading factor that defines the level of students' training.

In this context, the goal of the present study is to determine the influence of different types of motivation in humanities students on their academic performance and level of professional training.

2. Methods

The strategy of our research design relied on the case study method, which enabled the investigation of the features of students' motivation given the specifics and challenges of cases (Turashbek et al., 2023). The study proceeded from the hypothesis that there is a correlation between the indicators of motivation and academic performance in students in the studied groups. The study was conducted among students studying philological and psychological disciplines at universities. The research sample consisted of 62 respondents, full-time 2nd and 3rd year undergraduate students, of which 51 were female and 11 were male. The average age of the respondents was 20 years.

In the first stage of the study, the students' academic performance was determined proceeding from educational documentation. The primary criterion for the assessment of performance was the average grade (on a 5-point scale) in the last two academic semesters.

In the second stage, diagnostic methods were utilized to assess various parameters of student motivation. The diagnostic methods employed included:

- T. Ehlers' method assessing the motivation to achieve success,
- Iu.M. Orlov's questionnaire on the need for achievement,
- T.I. Ilyina's method for the study of learning motivation in higher education institutions.

The third stage involved the systematization and analysis of the results. The mathematical processing of the data using Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied to test for the presence of correlations between the indicators of motivation and academic performance. Student's t-test was used to identify the statistical significance of differences in learning motivation indicators between the groups with different levels of academic performance.

Statistical data processing was performed using Statistica 7.0 software.

3. Results

The indicators of the students' academic performance according to educational documentation are provided in Table 1.

Table 1
Indicators of the level of academic performance

Level of academic performance	Academic performance indicators (n=62)	
	abs.	%
High (4.5-5 points)	9	14
Average (3.5-4.5 points)	39	62
Low (less than 3.5 points)	14	24

Source: Authors development

Most students demonstrated average academic performance (62%); a high level of performance was found in 14%, and a low level was observed in 24%.

The respondents' motivation for success was assessed using Ehlers' motivation for success test (Table 2).

Table 2
Indicators of the level of motivation for success depending on academic performance

Motivation for success	Student group						Overall indicators (n=62)	
	high performance, n=9		average performance, n=39		low performance, n=14		bs.	%
	bs.	%	bs.	%	bs.	%		
High		88.9	9	74.4		50	4	71.0
Average		11.1		23.0		28.6	4	22.6
Low		-		2.6		21.4		6.4

Source: Authors development

A substantial aspect of the study was the assessment of the level of achievement motivation using Orlov's Need to Achieve the Goal questionnaire (Table 3).

Table 3
Indicators of motivation for achievement depending on academic performance

Motivation for achievement	Student group						Overall indicators (n=62)	
	high performance, n=9		average performance, n=39		low performance, n=14		bs.	%
	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%		
High	6	6.7	3	7.7	1	.1	0	6.1
Average	3	3.7	32	82.1	7	0	2	7.8
Low		-	4	10.2	6	2.9	0	6.1

Source: Authors development

Learning motivation was tested using Ilyina's Motivation of Learning in Higher Education method (Table 4).

Table 4
Indicators of the predominant type of learning motivation depending on academic performance

Predominant type of motivation for studying in higher education	Student group						Overall indicators (n=62)	
	high performance, n=9		average performance, n=39		low performance, n=14			
	bs.		bs.		bs.		bs.	
Knowledge acquisition		5.6	2	6.4		8.6	1	0.0
Mastering the profession		4.4	2	0.8		5.7	1	3.8
Obtaining the diploma				2.8		5.7	0	6.2

Source: Authors development

Analysis of data on the students' learning motivation and the different levels of academic performance revealed a relationship between final academic performance and the type of motivation according to Ilyina's method (Table 5).

Table 5
Results on learning motivation in students at different levels of academic performance based on Ilyina's method (M±m), points

Motivation scale	Student group			p
	high performance, n=9 (group 1)	average performance, n=39 (group 2)	low performance, n=14 (group 3)	
Knowledge acquisition	10.52±0.34	9.17±0.24	8.13±0.25	p<0.05; p1<0.001; p2<0.05
Mastering the profession	7.84±0.25	6.96±0.32	6.32 ±0.23	p<0.05; p1<0.001; p2>0.05
Obtaining the diploma	4.26±0.17	5.32±0.22	9.14±0.18	p <0.001; p1<0.001; p2<0.001

Source: Authors development

Note: p – reliability of differences between the indicators of the students in group 1 and group 2; p_1 – reliability of differences between the indicators of the students in group 1 and group 3; p_2 – reliability of differences between the indicators of the students in group 2 and group 3.

4. Discussion

Our study showed that most respondents had a high level of motivation for achievement (71%). In our view, this finding gives evidence of the students striving for achievements in education and personal development. An average level of achievement motivation was found in 22.6%, and a low level was demonstrated by 6.4% (Table 2). Correlation analysis through Pearson's coefficient proved the presence of a connection between academic performance and motivation for success ($r=0.284$, $p<0.05$).

Most students with high academic performance showed a high level of success motivation (88.9%), with the rest having an average level of this type of motivation. The students with average academic performance also predominantly had a high level of success motivation (74.4%), with only 23% showing an average level. Half of the students with low academic performance also demonstrated a high level of motivation for success.

This suggests that the studied students tended to have a high level of success motivation regardless of their academic success (Pelevin et al., 2023). Low motivation for success was found only in students with low academic performance, which generally agrees with previous studies (Semenova, 2015; Otrokov et al., 2023).

The assessment of achievement motivation (Table 3) showed that 67.8% had a low level of this type of motivation, and average and low levels were found in 16.1%, each. In this respect, we agree with the conclusions of O. Gorlova et al. (2023) in that such students do not have a pronounced striving to achieve the pursued results. In our study, Pearson's correlation coefficient revealed a relationship between students' academic performance and achievement motivation ($r=0.323$, $p<0.05$).

A comparison of the levels of academic performance and achievement motivation indicated that the students with high academic performance tended to have a high level of motivation for achievement (66.7%). In turn, the students with average performance predominantly had average achievement motivation (82.1%), similar to half of the students with low academic performance.

Analysis of the predominant type of motivation, as well as each motivation scale, in each student individually (Table 4) demonstrated that half of the students had knowledge acquisition as the leading motivation. This is a very favorable trend, since, according to A.N. Sokolnikov (2018), it shows students' focus on learning, deepening their knowledge, and self-development, even if this knowledge will not be used for professional purposes.

We also found that 33.8% were oriented toward mastering their profession. This trend positively characterizes the condition of education in the university and refutes the belief that students' need for professional knowledge is low and they have no desire to use it in the future. Finally, 16.2% were focused on obtaining a diploma. This share was relatively low, which gives hope that most students pursue higher education consciously and choose the profession that corresponds to their professional interests and dispositions.

The study also showed that the predominant type of motivation in 55.6% of the students with high academic performance was knowledge acquisition, and in 44.4%, it was mastery of the chosen profession. The students with average academic performance demonstrated approximately the same results, with the leading focus on knowledge acquisition (56.4%), motivation for mastery of the profession in second place (30.8%), and obtaining the diploma in the last place (12.8%).

Comparative analysis proved the presence of a positive correlation between students' high and average performance and their motivation to obtain professionally valuable knowledge, which agrees with the findings of M. Borodina et al. (2023).

As a result of mathematical analysis (Table 6), the highest values on the "Knowledge acquisition" scale were found in students with high academic performance (10.52 ± 0.34 points). This result with high reliability differs from that of students with average (9.17 ± 0.24 points, $p < 0.05$) and low (8.13 ± 0.25 points, $p_1 < 0.001$) performance. A comparison of the students with average and low motivation also revealed a reliable difference ($p_2 < 0.05$). This demonstrates the predominance of cognitive motives among academically successful students and the weakening of knowledge acquisition motivation in students with a low level of academic performance, which goes in line with the results of L. Shebzukhova et al. (2023).

A similar relationship between motivation and academic performance was observed with respect to the "Mastering of the profession" scale. The academically successful students scored 7.84 ± 0.25 points on this scale, which is reliably higher than students with average performance (6.96 ± 0.32 points, $p < 0.05$) and low performance (6.32 ± 0.23 points, $p_1 < 0.001$). There is no reliable difference between the results of students with average and high academic performance ($p_2 > 0.05$). Thus, professional motives were more characteristic of high-performing students and were less prominent among students with lower levels of performance, as has been previously demonstrated by I. Aleksandrova et al. (2023).

The highest results on the scale of "Obtaining the diploma" was observed in the group of low academic performance (9.14 ± 0.18 points). The students with average performance came in second place with 5.32 ± 0.22 points. All groups differed by this parameter with a high level of reliability ($p, p_1, p_2 < 0.001$), which points to a negative relationship between academic performance and the negative type of learning motivation.

Thus, higher-performing students were more focused on obtaining professional knowledge and skills, unlike low-performing students driven by superficial motives to achieve the primary goal of obtaining a diploma.

The empirical study also discovered a correlation between motivation for success and achievement motivation ($r=0.313$, $p<0.05$). This finding indicates that students with a high level of success motivation also tend to demonstrate high motivation for achievement. Furthermore, the strivings to acquire professional skills, master the chosen profession, and achieve success were found to correlate with each other ($r=0.179$, $p<0.05$). That is, students interested in further professional development are motivated to succeed and set high goals (e.g., to work in large companies, to obtain a second education that requires professional knowledge of foreign languages, to develop their own professional projects). Furthermore, a connection was revealed between the focus on obtaining a diploma and motivation for achievement ($r=0.164$, $p<0.05$).

5. Conclusion

The conducted diagnostics uncovered the following trends. Most of the studied students had an average level of academic performance. In the structure of the students' learning motivation, the positive motives, i.e., "Knowledge acquisition" and "Mastering the profession", dominated over negative, i.e., "Obtaining the diploma", which characterizes the motivation of these students as high in quality. Cognitive and professional motives were predominant in the students with high and average academic performance, while pragmatic motives were stronger in the students with a low level of knowledge. These results testify to the favorable influence of positive motivation on students' academic performance and, consequently, on the level of their professional training.

Thus, the quantitative and qualitative analysis of empirical results proved that higher motivation is associated with students' greater success in learning. This conclusion demonstrates the need for research on motivation to determine its dynamics throughout university education. Furthermore, we see promise in the introduction of innovative pedagogical methods to improve learning motivation in the educational process, as well as in the study of the effect of these methods on students' academic performance.

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